

Structural and mechanical properties of sputtered W₂N-Ti multilayer thin films

Shahid Anwar,* Sharmistha Anwar and Pravati Nayak

CSIR – Institute of Minerals and Materials Technology, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India-751013

Email: shahidanwr@gmail.com; Mob: 9337185511

Abstract

Protection of materials by applying hard coatings over it is one of the important and versatile means of improving component performance by reducing friction, increasing wear resistance and increasing its life. Multilayer coatings with combination (10BL, 20BL & 30BL) of transition-metal nitride (tungsten nitride, W₂N) and ductile interlayers (Ti) were deposited by reactive DC magnetron sputtering technique on silicon substrates. Structural and Mechanical properties of the deposited samples were analyzed by GIXRD, FESEM, EDX and nanoindentation tests. GIXRD result confirms the presence of cubic W₂N phase. FESEM image shows periodic arrangement of W₂N and Ti. Mechanical parameters like hardness, elastic modulus & resistance to plastic deformation were calculated. The effect of different factors e.g. ceramic/ metal (C/M) ratio, interlayer material and interface on mechanical properties were discussed. These results indicate that these factors play a dominant role in defining mechanical properties. The best mechanical properties was observed for 20 BL in comparison with 10BL and 30BL coating and has been attributed to higher ceramic to metal thickness ratio.

Keywords: Multilayer; Hard Coating; Hardness; Sputtering; nanoindentation,

Figure: (a) Cross-sectional FESEM & EDAX and (b) Hardness Vs Ceramic/Metal ratio of W₂N/Ti multilayer.

Reference:

1. Shahid Anwar and S Anwar, *Surface Engineering* 33 (4), 276-281, 2017
2. Shahid Anwar, and Sharmistha Anwar, *Surfaces and Interfaces* (2018-Inpress)